

Pinocchio paradox in scientific publications, Yours truly, I or we are lying

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Abstract

The wooden nose of Pinocchio, in Carlos Collodi's literary creation, would grow on lying. Geppetto, the woodcarver of Pinocchio, would cut the wooden nose when growth was proportional to the lies. The prose of science expressed in scientific publications has acquired the "Pinocchio paradox," resulting in fake peer-reviewed papers blurring Richard Dawkins' "science as the poetry of reality." In this short communication, **the Pinocchio paradox** is used as an allegory to interpret fake papers.

Keywords: Pinocchio's paradox, allegory, lies, blurred reality, fake papers,

A paper that requires multiple readings describes the Pinocchio paradox(Smith PE & Smith VE, 2010). One aspect of this paper was that Pinocchio's nose keeps growing in the future tense on telling lies. This presentation makes a pragmatic interpretation of the Pinocchio paradox by the statement, "Yours truly I or we are lying," an aspect of entertainment in the global political, Twitter, and fake news sphere. However, the growing number of fake papers, including peer-reviewed ones in science, is of great concern since it diminishes the civilizing influence of science.

Take the case of Ike Antkare, as reported: "But perhaps even more bizarrely in the academic world of metrics (although in this field it is hard to judge) is that you do not even have to exist to be world-renowned on Google Scholar. Take the case of Ike Antkare, who was outed as a fake in 2010 in a paper purporting to be written by himself. At that time, he had 102 publications and an h-index of 94, which at that time was less than Freud's (h-index of 183) but better than Einstein in the 36th position with an h-index of 84. Using one of the other Google metrics, the hm-index, Ike Antkare was in the sixth position outclassing all scientists in his field (computer science). This was carried out using a computer program that generated fake papers, which each referenced all the other papers generated. All that had to happen to be included on Google Scholar was to refer in the paper to a paper already referenced in Google Scholar. Once on Google Scholar, of course, there were then references to Ike in all the other

metrics-generating systems "(Laubbe, 2010; Wykes et al., 2013). This “fake” was reported in not-so-high-impact journals in 2010 and 2013. In 2020, MIT Press published **Ike Antkare, His publications, and those of His Disciples as a chapter** in the following reference. (Biagioli & Lippman, 2020)

“Pinocchio’s nose” grew in the future tense. In 2021 the journal Nature in views section gave a list of journal editors of decent journals (peer-reviewed) expressing their views. The views of one journal editor are reported here. Laura Fisher, the executive editor of RSC Advances, reported 68 papers from the journal were retracted due to falsified research. Here the editor describes that companies generate scientific manuscripts on order. The iconic word for a paper-producing mill for writing has been used to describe the production of fake papers as paper mills and tadpole paper mills. In effect, it is characterized as **industrialized cheating**.

A description of **zombie papers** is described as follows. “Fraudulent manuscripts can be submitted to multiple journals simultaneously, so even if an editor rejects it during peer review, they might see it published elsewhere. **“ Pinocchio’s nose” has taken a detour here and acquired a new growth pathway.** Jana Christopher, an image integrity analyst of FEBS letters, has blown the bugle on the systematic fabrication of scientific images and advised pre-publication image screening (Else, H & Noorden VR 2021: Christopher J, 2018). Another extract goes like this “The publishing giant Elsevier is withdrawing around 500 fake conference papers from one of its materials science journals. Many of the manuscripts, peer-reviewed, published in *Materials Today: Proceedings*, are off-topic, incomprehensible to the point of nonsense, or seem to have been written by software. They all seem to have come from conferences that never happened, possibly created by paper mills as a way to ‘launder’ publications (Kramer, 2022).

Since these papers are peer-reviewed, accepted, published, and then discovered to be fake, the paradox “yours truly (peer-reviewed) I or we are lying (fake found) comes full circle. Is this the tip of the iceberg, or are there many more fake papers? A preprint is apprehensive about artificial intelligence techniques being used to generate fake Western blots (Qi C et al., 2020 {cited in Else, H & Noorden VR 2021 }) , [What Is the Western BlotTest? | Sciencing](#)). Generating images using artificial intelligence may be extended for misuse in other areas of science.

Conclusion : Geppetto's algorithm as counter artificial intelligence(CAI) has to be formulated to cut out the fakery of images and fake papers for the **prose of science (papers) to come near the poetry of reality** (Fortey, 2013)

Dedication: This article is dedicated to my maternal grandfather late G Ramasubramania Iyer (GRI) , who translated “ The Adventures of Pinocchio” into Tamil as “ பின்னோச்சியோ, ஒரு மரப்பாவையின் கதை” (Pinocchio , a wooden puppet's story) with due copyright acquired from the original publishers. GRI did this translation in Ambasamudram, a village in Tirunelveli district, Tamil Nadu, India . First Tamil edition came out in November , 1962 . Printed by Progressive printers, Chennai.

No potential conflict of interest.

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